

THE CURRENT RELEVANCE OF PRE-SCHOOL AGE VISUALLY IMPAIRED CHILDREN'S PREPARATION FOR SCHOOL FROM THE POINT OF SPEECH

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Abstract. *This article is written about the current importance of pre-school visually impaired children's verbal preparation for school, the specific aspects of the speech of visually impaired children, the necessary preparatory work for children to learn the Braille alphabet.*

Keywords: *pre-school, speech impairment, dyslalia, dysarthria, NTR, FFN, isolation, negativism.*

It's no secret that our eyes are not only an important part of receiving information, but also embody feelings. The eye is an analyzer that receives 70% of the information about the environment. Visually impaired children are characterized by their limited perception of the world around them and their reliance on skin-tactile and auditory perception. Speech impairment in visually impaired children is a secondary limitation in which certain connections and interactions between speech and visual impairment can be observed.

Speech disorders in visually impaired children can be defined according to the degree of preservation of vision. The formation of speech in such children is related to the fact that it takes place in much more difficult conditions than in a sighted child, it is formed on a pathological basis in the perception of the surrounding world. Due to the violation of the activity of the visual analyzer, children, as a rule, do not have a real, clear idea about the surrounding world and its various objects and events. The lack of emotional experience in preschool-age visually impaired children is manifested by the specificity of speech development, which often does not correspond to the usual age limits.

Due to the malfunction of the visual analyzer, the speech of children with visual pathology is characterized by certain features: the lack of necessary vocabulary - verbalism, that is, the violation of the semantic side of the word that is not related to the visual image of the object, echolalia - the child's automatic (uncontrolled) repetition of other people's words, complete phrases or their parts and even whole sentences, early development of speech.

Preschool children with vision problems are characterized by a lack of field and spatial images, inability to identify spatial signs and directions in speech. The ability to distinguish the properties of objects, to find generalizing words is significantly behind the norm.

As a result of the insufficient objective images of reality, it becomes difficult to keep detailed statements in the speech memory and the correct grammatical construction of the sentence. A qualitative decline in speech development is observed when performing tasks to describe real-world objects. There is a sharp lag in the development of phonemic hearing, sound analysis and synthesis, primary reading skills. There is also a delay in the development of a number of important functions related to the formation of the speech system (praxis, gnosis, coordination, spatial orientation, reduced motor skills, both general and fine motor skills).

Deficits in speech development limit the already narrowed range of communication of visually impaired children, which makes it difficult to form a number of personal characteristics or leads to the appearance of negative characteristics (isolation, negativism, etc.).

Research by scientists has shown that 80-90% of visually impaired children suffer from underdeveloped speech, which manifests itself in various forms: dyslalia, dysarthria, NTR, FFN.

Partial or complete vision impairment leads to serious impairments in the field of emotional cognition, which in turn affects the process of speech development. Therefore, the correction of speech disorders in visually impaired children is carried out taking into account not only the speech defect, but also the state of vision, the characteristics of the methods of perception and the specific methods of presenting the same material in the educational process.

Many foreign scientists have studied speech characteristics of visually impaired children in their scientific works: L.S. Volkova, L.S. Vygotsky, G.V. Grigoreva, V.B. Gudopis, M.I. Zemseva, E.A. Kultush, A.T. Litvak, D.M. Mallyayev, L.I. Plaksina, L.I. According to Sonsev, the lack of information about the environment in visually impaired children causes changes and slowness in the process of visual perception to make the information about the existence surrounding them unclear. All this has a negative impact on the development of the communication process, and it becomes a secondary limitation for children with disabilities.

Until now, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, there has been little scientific research on the speech of visually impaired children of preschool age. Therefore, we believe that this topic should be studied in Uzbekistan.

When the child turns six years old, parents think about which school to go to. They are faced with the question of how to prepare him for school, what is necessary for him to study successfully. We need to find solutions to the problems that arise in preparing visually impaired children for school.

Entering school is the stage of recognition of the child's new socially important position. At school, children are introduced to new activities, which are valued by both children and adults as serious activities with social recognition.

The moment of transition to school, despite the preparations made in the family, always brings new conditions for the child, new, regulated requirements, difficulties caused by increased responsibility for his work.

Children are often forced to leave their villages or towns because not every town has a special school for blind children. Children should learn to obey teacher's demands, regardless of their interest in work, they should have the ability to organize their activities according to teacher's assignment. All these qualities should already be nurtured in the family, because applying and using the skills formed even in new conditions creates great difficulties for children. These difficulties are secondary disorders of psychological development caused by blindness (the wrong way in space vision, defects in the development of motor skills, etc.), as well as general, non-specific diseases of blindness (reduced working capacity, increased fatigue, etc.) are characterized. These disorders often disappear during the preschool period, and their elimination remains the task of the school period.

Currently, the programs developed in schools for blind children require from the children who enter the school not only to have great knowledge, but also the ability to use certain methods of working with educational materials in their activities. Mastering these methods of work implies the ability to control one's own behavior, the systematic performance of mental work in a class

group under the guidance of a teacher, that is, the existence of a level of mental development characterized as readiness to study at school.

Psychological preparation for school consists of motivational, volitional, mental preparation in the field of relationships, that is, it includes the development of a number of mental formations that give the child the opportunity to systematically acquire school knowledge. This is, first of all, the emergence of cognitive interest, interest in learning in a special activity aimed at direct and direct learning - that is, the formation of educational activities.

For a visually impaired child (including a child with residual vision), the main means of obtaining information about the surrounding objects is touch. Therefore, all children should be taught to examine objects by touch.

In familiarizing the child with the surrounding objects, not only touch and residual vision, but also hearing are involved. Therefore, attention should be paid to the development of auditory perception. First of all, the child should develop the ability to listen.

The study of geometric shapes and their properties is an important part of the work of parents in the formation of spatial imagination in a blind child, which is the most difficult area of mental development, which is associated with the lack of or weakening of vision.

One of the main tasks of preparing a child for school is preparing him to learn to read and write according to the L. Braille system. Writing with a stylus requires a lot of muscle tension from children. Hands get tired very quickly in uneducated children, children lose interest in learning.

There are a number of exercises for the development of the muscles of the fingers and the hands in general, which parents of children entering special schools need to know. Therefore, it is necessary to scientifically study this topic and develop recommendations for parents.

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